

Language Learning & Teaching and Instruction Technology Conference at

Ajou University
in Tashkent

December 23rd 2023

"Transforming English Teaching and Learning:
Unveiling Strategies for Engaging and
Empowering Learners in Academia"

Introduction

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Challenges in Language Learning

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Need of Revolutionizing English Education

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Tactics for Captivating Learners

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Power of Innovative Teaching

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Impact of AI in Language Acquisition

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Conclusion / Question & Answer

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PRESENTATION OUTLINE

What you think?

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Why should students attend lessons at university when the required learning material is available online?

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Reasons to Attend University:

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- The presentation explores the strategies that captivate and empower learners, create a teaching world that sparks curiosity, foster critical thinking and enable learners to actively participate in their educational journey, unlocking the full potential of English Education through an immersive learning experience.

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Challenges in Language Learning

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- Linguistic Complexity
- Cultural and Contextual Factors
- Individual Differences
- Speaking & Listening Skills
- Vocabulary Acquisition
- Language Anxiety
- Limited Exposure & Practice
- Assessment & Feedback
- Time & Persistence

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If it doesn't challenge you, it doesn't change you!

Tactics for Engaging Learners

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**Learner Centric
Approach**

**Technology &
Multimedia Resources**

**Project Based &
Experiential Learning**

Engaging Techniques

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Student's Autonomy

Active Learning

Individualized
Instruction

Reflection

Collaboration &
Communication

Authentic Assessment

Power of Innovative Teaching

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Quizlet

Kahoot!

:Padlet

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Transforming English Education with AI

Enhance learner's Engagement & Facilitate personalized learning journey

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Focus on specific needs, progress at their own pace

Making language learning enjoyable

Provides real time feedback

Generate Engaging Content

Improve Student learning Outcome

Enable learners to correct errors

Provide Valuable Insights

Language learning becomes efficient and effective

Examples of using AI in English Edu.

- Wordtune - Unlock creativity and improve writing on the sentence level.
- GPT Zero - Advanced AI detector for Chat GPT
- Interviewby.ai - Add job description and it will generate interview questions, record answers in your voice and get feedback.
- Getbuddies.co - Students can design their own English speaking friend
- Excuses.ai- Excuse generator
- Slides go - Creating Power point presentation

Maximize Impact of AI in Language Acquisition

- Identify Clear Goal and Objectives
- Integrate AI tools and platform seamlessly in curriculum
- Ensure Data Privacy and Security Measures
- Train Educators for Effectively Utilization
- Foster Collaboration between AI developer, educator and experts
- Promote equality and inclusivity
- Prioritize Ethics

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Conclusion

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- By investing in innovative pedagogies, supportive learning environments, and ongoing professional development, we can create a transformative educational experience that empowers learners, fosters their growth, and builds a brighter future for all.
- Together, let us embark on a journey to engage learners in academia and unlock their full potential.

Any Questions

Thankyou

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